

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: CONCEPT, STRUCTURE AND LEGAL REGULATION

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Abstract: The study examines management as a multi-level process of coordination and control, and also analyzes its legal and social aspects. Particular attention is paid to public administration, its functions, structure and role in regulating social processes. The key characteristics of state power and its influence on law and order and the development of society are identified.

Keywords: Management, public administration, coordination, control, public authority, regulation, legislation.

Management is a complex and multi-level process that involves organizing, coordinating and controlling actions to achieve specific goals. In a broad sense, it covers both tangible and intangible aspects of performance, including decision making, planning and monitoring. In the legal field, management acquires special importance, since it is aimed at implementing legal norms, enforcing legislation and regulating public relations.

There are different approaches to defining management. So, U.A. Tikhomirov considers it as a process of purposeful influence of a subject on an object in order to change its state. K. Nazarov emphasizes that management is social in nature, as it is connected with the activities of people and the organization of social processes. In turn, T. Parsons highlights the ability of management to adapt to changing conditions, which is especially important in a dynamic social environment.

A systematic approach to management is reflected in the works of V.D. Eremenko, who views it as a process aimed at streamlining phenomena and eliminating uncertainty. F.W. Taylor, one of the founders of the scientific approach to management, emphasized the need to combine practical activities with scientific principles. Thus, management is not only a coordination process, but also a scientifically based system aimed at effectively achieving goals.

Public administration is a type of management activity carried out within the framework of public authority. It is aimed at implementing government functions, ensuring the rule of law and achieving socially significant goals. Unlike management in the private sector, public management is based on legal norms and is carried out by government agencies.

G.Elinek defines public administration as the practical activities of authorities aimed at creating, regulating and terminating public relations in the

interests of the state and society . L. Stein interpreted public administration as the implementation of the state will expressed in law, which emphasizes its normative and legal nature . According to F. Nigro and L. Nigro, public administration covers the activities of all three branches of government, including legislative regulation, execution of government programs and judicial control over their implementation .

A special role in public administration is played by its structure and functions. G.V. Atamanchuk views it as the organizing and regulating activities of the state aimed at streamlining social processes . U.A. Tikhomirov identifies such key features of public administration as continuity, functional specialization, the use of administrative measures and the hierarchical structure of government bodies. These characteristics highlight the importance of state power in ensuring stability, law and order and social development.

Public administration performs many functions, including the development and implementation of public policy, monitoring compliance with legislation, and regulating economic and social processes. It is aimed at protecting the rights of citizens, maintaining public order and developing state institutions.

Modern researchers such as V.E. Chirkin, consider public administration as a process of regulating relations between the state, society and the individual . It is based on coordinating the interests of various social groups and ensuring effective interaction between government institutions and the population. According to I.V. Ponkin, public administration is a mechanism for implementing state power, including control, regulatory and target functions .

An important aspect of public administration is its ability to adapt to changes in the economic, social and political spheres.

As noted by V.G. Afanasyev, management must take into account environmental factors and ensure the sustainability of state institutions . This is especially true in the context of globalization, when demands on the efficiency of government mechanisms and the quality of management decision-making increase.

Conclusion

Public administration is a complex and multifaceted process that ensures the implementation of government functions, compliance with law and order and the effective regulation of public relations. Being a special form of management activity, it is based on regulations, institutional mechanisms and strategic planning, which allows the state to adapt to dynamically changing conditions and solve socio-economic problems.

The variety of scientific approaches to the concept of management indicates its interdisciplinary nature. Theoretical works of domestic and foreign researchers emphasize the importance of systemic, legal and organizational aspects of management, its role in ensuring stability and sustainable development of society. Particular importance is given to public administration as an instrument for the implementation of public power, aimed at achieving the public good, maintaining the rule of law and improving the quality of life of citizens.

The effectiveness of public administration largely depends on its ability to adapt to external challenges, improve control and regulation methods, and introduce innovative approaches to management practice. In modern conditions, when significant transformations are taking place in the economic, social and technological spheres, public administration must combine traditional mechanisms with new management models, which will ensure its sustainability and efficiency.

Thus, public administration plays a key role in the formation and development of public institutions, being an integral element of the rule of law. Its further improvement requires an integrated approach that takes into account modern challenges and prospects, which will ensure a high level of legal regulation, stability and socio-economic development of the country.

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